

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ANALYTICAL STRATEGIES AS A TOOL OF ENTERTAINMENT

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to identify the spectrum of entertainment analytical strategies of speech mask presented in the communicative space of entertainment television; to identify their role in the construction of the communicative space. The following strategies of speech mask are revealed: strategies of speech masks *Provocateur*, *Moralist*, *Critic*. Their object is stories of "human interest": events and situations of everyday life, interpersonal relationships. It should be noted that the strategies under analysis organize the composition of an entertaining text according to a *sporadic* model.

Keywords: television, entertainment TV, discourse, communicative strategy, speech mask, entertainment.

One of the most important, central categories of media text is the image of the author, which structures and organizes other components of the text. In modern television discourse, the addresser is more and more clearly explicated. The study of the author's image at this level is connected with the study of the concept of a linguistic personality, a verbal author. The verbal author is a special communicative strategy of the speech mask, the compositional center of the media text. The journalist's speech mask is a component of the author's image in the text, situational communicative role [3]. M.V. Shpilman defines speech mask strategy as "a special type of communicative strategy based on the temporary and situational exploitation of someone else's linguistic image, which the speaker reconstructs and appropriates for a specific purpose; this is an imitation of someone else's speech behavior, including a different manner of speech, a different vocabulary" [9: 16-17]. The speech mask outlines the typical features of speech behavior, "condensing and concretizing them" [8: 17-18].

A journalist while building and controlling the verbal and non-verbal aspects of his behavior, exposes himself in various ways in communicative situations due to his professional activities. The model of speech behavior, with the help of which the TV presenter changes his own image, is a speech mask. Organizing the communicative space in the conditions of the struggle for attention, the interest of the media audience, the author/addresser of entertainment programs constantly re-emphasizes the genre form by changing the model of speech behavior, moving from entertaining, emotionally rich to neutral, instructive or accusatory.

In order to present the peculiarities of modern entertainment TV discourse and the role of entertainment analytical strategies of speech masks (further – SM) in it, let us consider the concept of entertainment discourse. Its key function is a recreational function that combines a number of functions: stress relief (recreation and relaxation), anxiety reduction; escaping, emotionally affecting [2]. Entertainment discourse to some extent correlates with gaming discourse. The system-forming feature of these types of communication is a game worldview aimed at the carnivalization of being

and the creative transformation of the experienced reality.

Thematic characteristics of entertaining discourse cover a wide range of fascinating, entertaining, funny information, the tonality accentuates the emotional attitude to reality [7: 94-95]. Signs of entertainment that characterize entertainment discourse are "maximum variety, maximum expressiveness, no psychology", captivating narration, a dynamically developing plot, intrigue, energetic pace, humor, beautiful actors, attractive outfits, etc." [4: 26].

At the same time, according to the fair statement of S.N. Akinfieva, entertainment is not only pleasure, relaxation and positive that the audience receives when watching programs. Entertainment is "something that makes consciousness function, something that allows a person to become aware of himself in the reality around him, some components due to which entertainment acquires a socially significant meaning" [2]. Researchers talk about several complementary components of entertainment programs: cognitive (television quizzes), socio-pedagogical (reality shows that affirm certain behaviors, their acceptability / inacceptability), integrative (talk shows that show the commonality of problems and the ability to solve them regardless of social, confessional, national, gender and other characteristics of the participants). Simultaneously with satisfying the need for rest, relaxation, the viewer receives a socio-psychological charge by observing the behavior of the characters, borrowing their behavior patterns, experiencing the situation with them, following the turns in the discussion of the hosts, at the same time correlating everything with their own lives [6].

Any emotionally charged public discussion with a large number of studio participants and behind the screen is due to a certain problem that worries people [1: 443]. As a result, the addresser of the entertaining discourse, in addition to the game/entertainment strategies of the speech mask, has to try on masks of a different nature, demonstrating the seriousness of the problem under discussion and its significance for people. At the same time, entertainment remains the dominant feature of communication. Thus, it is relevant to identify the repertoire of the speech mask strategy in the entertainment television discourse.

The *purpose* of this article is to identify the spectrum of entertainment analytical strategies of speech mask presented in the communicative space of entertainment television, to identify their role in the construction of the communicative space.

The group of entertaining analytical strategies of speech mask strategies is associated with the intentions of the author to present a point of view regarding the peculiarities of the functioning of various socio-cultural spheres or areas of everyday life. At the same time, it is not characteristic of entertainment programs, according to S.N. Akinfieva, analyticity and "the desire to look deep" [2] in modern entertainment programs is actively combined with such signs of entertainment as lightness, stress relief, relaxation and rest. The emotionality inherent in entertainment television is represented in the entertaining analytical strategies of the speech mask. As a result, in the genres of talk shows, reality shows, due to the combination of entertaining and quasi-serious (discussion of "eternal" moral values, the problems of Goodness, Love, Beauty, the meaning of life, etc. in an entertaining shell), a special spectacle is formed.

Entertaining analytical speeches of the speech mask are represented by the strategies of the SM *Provocateur*, *Moralist*, *Critic*. Their object is stories of "human interest": events and situations of everyday life, interpersonal relationships.

The strategy of the SM *Provocateur* is to deliberately activate, encourage the addressee to think, form an attitude to the subject of speech. It is most typical for the genres of reality shows with elements of the author's commentary (fixed in 59% of reality show), talk shows (66%). At the same time, the absence of a negative component, often characteristic of provocative behavior, is characteristic, with a pronounced emphasis on stimulation, an invitation to reflection, or a playful beginning. In this case, the author enters into a game with the addressee, involving him as a Co-thinker.

The communicative behavior of the *Provocateur* is characterized by the absence or (rarely) feigned conflict, a high degree of preparedness, and the absence or low proportion of the addressee's reaction taken into account. The tactics that characterize the communicative behavior of this speech mask are the tactics of an ironic provocateur and the tactics of provoking the addressee's thoughts.

The tactic of an ironic provocateur is aimed at creating playful statements expressing mockery or crafty allegory in order to provoke reflection and entertain the viewer. Language markers are expressions expressing a confrontational nature: *And I'm thinking; you forgive me, of course, but; interrogative form of statements*. In the presented episode, the host addresses the viewer, acting out a conversation with the heroine, who has endured domestic violence for a long time. Implemented in this case, bringing to the point of absurdity is aimed at expressing a negative attitude at the same time as emphasizing the unacceptability, the comic nature of the situation: *Of course, you will forgive me, but how much do you need? You, like Thumbelina, definitely couldn't take a hit on yourself. And was it worth it to get involved in this war, if you definitely can't emerge victorious? ... Just don't say that it wasn't enough for you. Well,*

yes, a broken arm, but there is also a nose, a leg (Three First Dates, 09/10/2021). At the same time, extralinguistic factors of communication are of great importance - a smile, gestures (a tilted head, spreading of hands), demonstrating a mocking attitude towards what was said.

The tactic of provoking the addressee's thoughts consists in demonstrating the author's opinion regarding the peculiarities of the characters' behavior in a particular situation by emphasizing actions that are non-standard and contrary to accepted norms. In the above episode, the author, speaking about the life situation of the heroine of the program, uses a form of unreal inclination, which relates the message to the plane of the possible or presumptive. The rhetorical question is aimed at engaging the viewer in co-reflection: *I sometimes think, what if she told her husband everything she thinks about him? ... This, of course, is a joke, but, on the other hand, maybe you don't need to show your true face, it's better to hide it behind a mask?* ("Three first dates", 04/16/2021). In this case, the journalist uses the tactics of a provocateur in order to attract attention, to involve the addressee in the situation unfolding on the screen.

In a number of cases, the *Provocateur* uses the tactics of provocative obtaining of information as a special, attractive basis for the development of the topic. In this case, verbal provocation is realized - "purposeful, motivated, predominantly controlled communicative behavior aimed at obtaining information that the interlocutor does not want to give out voluntarily, or destabilizing his emotional state" [5]. The attractiveness of tactics lies in the activation of the game principle. The attention of the viewer is intended to be attracted not so much by information as by psychological, dramatic (acted) collisions of communicants. For example, in the talk show "On the Hook" the author resorts to this tactical tool, expressing a special understanding of body modification, which, firstly, contradicts the description provided by the show's expert earlier, and secondly, requires further explanation by the expert, i.e. theme deployment. At the same time, the emphasis on the psychological impact on the partner (This is such an injection in the direction of Katya) is aimed at ensuring that the viewer follows how the situation will unfold:

Presenter 1: *But applying cosmetics is also body modification. This is such an injection towards Katya.*

Presenter: *Come on, this is the desire to make yourself more beautiful, probably cosmetics, because we are trying to achieve the same in this sense. Is it true? (referring to an expert, who further explains what body modification is)* (On the Hook, 01/17/2022). The provocative intention of the journalist is recognized and to a certain extent supported by the interlocutor: *come on* (a feigned insult, followed by a speech act of justification), at the same time it becomes a bridge for expanding the topic of the conversation.

The strategy of RM *Moralist* (characteristic of 4% of talk shows, reality shows - 28%) is associated with the intention of the communicator to moralize, broadcast moral values, discuss the problems of good and evil, love, the meaning of life. This strategy is most typical for the entertainment genres of talk shows, reality

shows. The arsenal of tools that construct the Moralists' speech behavior consists of tactics: commentary, advice, evaluation. So, the plot of the reality show "Three First Dates" is that a girl, in search of her soulmate, goes on three dates with potential boyfriends. A variety of communicative situations in which the characters find themselves are accompanied by the host's comments. The author addresses either the hero or conducts an auto monologue that involves the addressee. Interaction markers are rhetorical questions voicing doubts, misunderstanding, assessment, with which the addressee may agree due to the fact that they are based on a common presuppositional base: *Alexey, please tell me, are you looking for a mother for girls? I think there will be no problems with this. Yes, girls definitely need an example of female love and care nearby. Only then will she be able to grow into a full-fledged person* ("Three First Dates", 09/10/2021). Turning to the hero outside the situation of direct contact with him, the author essentially builds a dialogic interaction with the viewer, who is supposed to play the role of an Interlocutor-co-thinker. Rhetorical questions, value judgments, logically arising from the represented communicative situations, are aimed at creating an atmosphere of conversation among acquaintances discussing the life vicissitudes of other people.

In the next episode, the addresser uses the tactics of commentary, advice, trying to sort out human mores: *You said that your husband is to blame. Apparently, there were some actions that also contributed to this ... When there are children in the family, all attention is focused on them. The man begins to suffer.* (commentary tactics) *As a rule, there is your way out - involve a man in this process: pick up children, take them to different circles. Then men will definitely not have extra time for some third-party relationships* (advice tactics) ("Three First Dates", 04/16/2021). At the same time, the addressee's involvement in the dialogue is carried out through the creation of a universal basis for understanding, the representation of a well-known truth, with which the addressee will certainly agree. The author invites you to evaluate, weigh and think about what happened in the reality show.

Through the strategy of RM *Critic* (talk shows - 37%, reality shows - 6%), the intentions of an expert interpreter are realized. The critic analyzes, evaluates the socio-cultural, life realities discussed by the characters or the hosts in the studio. This strategy is most in demand in such genres as: infotainment programs, talk shows, interactive shows. Thus, the hosts of the women's talk show "A Day in the Big City", trying on the mask of the Critic, share their impressions of the concerts held in the capital. What is important here is not so much direct information about past events, but the introduction of elements of drama into the communicative space. The tactics of negative evaluation, detection of errors, verification of authenticity build a discourse with an emphasis not on the idea, but on depicting a dramatic situation that provokes the activation of emotions, the interest of the audience: (host 1) *I agree with you that when I see posters in Minsk, I suspect either in our homeland it no longer thunders so much, so we*

reach the expanses of Russia or Belarus. A lot of officially registered doubles come, yes, that is, Celentano ... they bring doubles most often ... in one of the large palaces of Minsk. Unfortunately, technically it was an unprepared event, the screens were not turned on, the speakers were not placed around the hall. (host 2) *I will complete you. But there is a performer. Yes, this is a creative unit... But there is also a host party, whose obligations include both the technical side and everything else that is not respected, unfortunately. If you had any story connected with some kind of concert performance of your favorite star. You are extremely disappointed, live phone ..., we are waiting for stories* ("A Day in the Big City", 30.03.2016). In the call to share stories and assessments, the viewer is involved in the discussion of the topic also as a Socratic. At the same time, the focus of attention is focused not so much on the information content of messages (ie, on the event that occurred), but on the release of negative emotions.

It should be noted that the strategies under analysis organize the composition of an entertaining text according to a *sporadic* model. It consists in random (from case to case) interspersing entertaining analytical strategies into the discursive continuum, their combination with game strategies, which provides a mosaic composition of the text. For example: *How ugly it is, to put it mildly. I would say mean. Did they not guess that their boy would grow up. They would have to resolve this issue on the shore. So it would be right* (tactics of evaluation, commentary, SM Critic). ... *Passions flare up. It is clear that after some time the hottest emotions fade away. What remains? Ivan has nothing left* (joking intonation, ironic facial expression) (tactics of ironic commentary) ["Three First Dates", 27.02.2022]; *But I'm thinking if Anastasia's husband asked for forgiveness, would she still stay with him, or was it a matter of principle?* (tactics of provoking the addressee's thoughts, SM Provocateur) ... *The conclusion is always the same, that nothing good can be built on a lie. I sometimes think that if I told my husband everything that I think about him, it's as if they parted ways a long time ago* (commentary tactics, SM Moralists) ("Three First Dates", 04/16/2021). Regular change of SM strategies exacerbates the development of the plot of the program, "revives" the media text, makes it dynamic. Humorous, playful strategies that surround entertaining analytical strategies, give them contrast, are designed to captivate and emotionally involve the viewer.

Thus, entertaining talk shows, reality shows, being hybrid discursive formations (combine the characteristics of entertainment, media types of discourse), integrate the characteristics of analytical discourse, which becomes a backbone feature of entertainment television discourse. The presentation of information in the conditions of an information explosion requires the introduction of various ways to attract the attention of the viewer. The tendency to spread entertainment is complemented/enriched by analyticism, in some way psychology, which mask the carnivalization of being and the creative transformation of experienced reality.

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THE VOCABULARY OF SCIENTIFIC WORKS IN THE 13th-16th CENTURIES TURKIC LANGUAGES

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Abstract

One of the distinguished styles in terms of functionality of literary language is scientific style. Scientific style has a long history in Turkic languages. Formulation of scientific style occurs in the highest stage of evolution of literary language. In this regard formation history of scientific styles in Turkic languages, in fact, reflects also the history of Turkic literary languages. Thus style differentiation informs about enhancing of expressing capabilities in the diversification of the language. The scientific style, which is one of the styles of language having a different position in terms of functionality, has its own internal laws. This regularity is mostly related to the lexical layer of the language. Thus, when clarifying the characteristics of the scientific style, first of all, it's taken into account that it's a term. The term characterizes the scientific style as a unit of language vocabulary and has functionality in a limited range. From the analysis of the lexical stock of the scientific style in the XIII-XIV centuries, it is clear that native terms are the core of the scientific style in the Turkic languages. Their percentage of usage varies from one field to another, and mainly in Turks it is possible to determine with it which sciences have a more ancient history. Native terminology as a part of the people's language is a special language layer with deep roots, having comprehensive usability and forming on the basis of different word-formation constructions.

Keywords: term, scientific style, vocabulary, loanwords, Turkic languages, Chagatai, Azerbaijani, Turkish, Kipchak, Karakhani.

Introduction

The styles that manifested using potential of language in society in different forms, at the same time, reflect the developmental perspectives of language in the form of various layers. As B. de Courtenay says, "Language is a complex category potentially existing and a continuously repeating process". The language units that are part of this dynamic and continuous complex process are realized differently within a specific sphere and environment. Distinctive realization and manifestation cause to internal divisions in language. In fact, this internal division occurs according to the principle of being used the language in the speech process. As a result, the style of using language is formed on the basis of differences in the process of thinking and comprehension in a specific language environment. Although this style manifesting in accordance with the general rules of language, it differs from other communicative levels of language by its conformity to specific norms and its specific frameworks of usage.

F.de Saussure writes pointing out the difference between language and speech: "The study of language activity is divided into two parts: the first of them is basic, its basis is language, it doesn't have essentially a social character and doesn't depend on the individuality. The second is secondary, speech activity is related to individuality, in other words, speech is related to speaking. Both subjects are closely related (Saussure, p.28). The individuality that the author discusses in the connection between language and speech coincides with the concept of style. It is intended to distinguish the individual and normative style from each other. Although both manifest in fact purely in the process of speech, a normative style is an act of language that follows the norms required at a concrete level of language. Although such norms are expected in the individual style itself, it appears as an individual approach and a unique speech variant of the language user. In fact, this is a historical process occurring in the language. Thus, at the same time, the most correct and right of the existing variants of speech in the language, or the most